

Kinetics and Mechanism of The Alkaline Copper (II) Asparagine Complex by The Hexacyanoferrate (III) Ion

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Abstract

The uncatalyzed reaction between copper (II) asparagine complex [CAC] and hexacyanoferrate (III) ion in alkaline medium has a stoichiometry of 1 : 4 with first-order dependence on hexacyanoferrate (III). The reaction is also first order with respect to [copper (II) asparagine] and fractional with [alkali]. A mechanism involving the formation of a complex between copper (II) asparagine and hexacyanoferrate (III) was proposed. The main oxidation products of the copper (II) asparagine complex were copper (II) oxide, 3-oxopropanamide, carbon dioxide, and ammonia. The effect of temperature was also studied for calculating kinetic data with respect to different reagents.

Keywords

Kinetics, Oxidation, Copper (II) Asparagine, Hexacyanoferrate (III), Complex.

Introduction

The latest researches in kinetic areas focus on the synthesis and oxidation of amino acids and their metal complexes due to their applicability in pharmacy, medicine, agronomy and nutrition [1,3,5,9,12]. Amino acids such as lysine, histidine and arginine are widely used as ligands due to their biological activities in the prevention of various diseases. These ligands react with metal ions, providing a solid foundation for further research[11]. Chemical kinetics includes not only the study of reaction rates, but also the extensive study of the effects of concentration, temperature, catalysts, etc. on reactions. In the last few decades, mechanistic studies of reactions involving solutions have gained considerable importance compared to gases[6]. Copper (II) complexes play important roles in a variety of chemical reactions. Copper (II) complexes possess several advantageous properties that make them attractive for photoredox catalysis. Copper also exhibits several accessible oxidation states, making both oxidative and reductive processes possible. This versatility allows copper (II) complexes to be involved in a wide range of redox reactions, making them suitable for a variety of transformations[10].

Objective of study

The objective of the present work is to study the formation of the copper (II) asparagine complex and its oxidation by the hexacyanoferrate (III) ion. The suitable mechanism was also proposed in alkaline medium by the given oxidant.

Review of Literature

Kinetics and mechanism of osmium (VIII) catalyzed oxidation of valine by hexacyanoferrate in alkaline medium was studied by Devra and Yadav (2022), Osmium (VIII) catalysed oxidation of diclofenac sodium by diperiodatoargentate (III) complex in aqueous alkaline medium was studied by Patil, et al (2009), Reaction kinetics of sonochemical oxidation of potassium hexacyanoferrate (II) in aqueous solutions was studied by Rajchel-Mieldzioc, et al (2020), Kinetics and mechanism of copper (II)-catalyzed oxidation of asparagine by sodium N chloro-p-toluene sulphonamide in alkaline media was studied by Sensagar and Yadav (1988), Synthesis, characterization of some complexes of copper (II) with l-asparagine, l-histidine, l-lysine was studied Tripathi and Kamal (2015) etc.

Methodology

Materials:

CuCl₂, Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O, CuSO₄·5H₂O, and sodium acetate were manufactured by Alfa Aesar, Great Britain. L-asparagine, sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide, potassium hydrogen phthalate, oxalic acid, and phenolphthalein were obtained from E. Merck (India) Ltd., and potassium hexacyanoferrate (III) was obtained from Fluka-Puris. Alkaline titration was used to determine the purity of L-asparagine. All solutions were prepared in double-distilled water.

Synthesis of Copper (II) asparagine complex [CAC]:

The asparagine-copper complex was prepared by reacting the metal ion and L-asparagine in a 2:1 molar ratio in triple-distilled water. Using various copper salts (Cu(NO₃)₂·3H₂O, CuSO₄·5H₂O, CuCl₂) and l-asparagine as ligands, the [Cu(asparagine)₂]⁺² complex was prepared. In this process, 2 mM amino acid was mixed with 2 mM sodium acetate in 20 mL of aqueous solution and shaken until a clear solution was formed. Then, 1 mM metal salt was added dropwise to 2 mL of

Fig. 1: log (Absorbance) vs Time plot for the oxidation of CAC

Effect of [OH⁻] and Ionic strength on the oxidation of CAC:

The reaction was tested at various temperatures by increasing the alkali concentration tenfold and the ionic strength fivefold. It was observed that the reaction deviated from zero order under the influence of the alkali, and the reaction speed increased with increasing ionic strength. These reactions were observed at various temperatures ranging from 303 K to 323 K, with a difference of 5°C. The data and graphs for the above experiments are shown in Table 1 and Figures 2 and 3.

Table 1: Effect of [OH⁻] and ionic strength on the hexacyanoferrate (III) oxidation of CAC

10^4 [CAC] = 10.0 mol dm⁻³, 10^4 [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻ = 20.0 mol dm⁻³ and μ = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

Temp. (K)	10^2 [OH ⁻] (mol dm ⁻³)				
	1	3	5	7.5	10
$10^{-2} k_{obs}$ (s ⁻¹)					
303	3.886	5.654	7.876	10.987	14.795
308	5.896	8.584	11.548	13.672	16.564
313	7.876	10.518	12.238	14.892	18.436
318	9.635	13.678	13.659	16.549	19.548
323	11.232	14.657	15.284	17.875	21.896

Fig. 2: k_o vs [OH⁻] plots for the oxidation of CAC

Fig 3: log k₀ vs plots for the oxidation of CAC

Dependence of k₀ on [CAC]:

To investigate the effect of the substrate on the reaction, the substrate concentration was increased 10-fold, and graphs of k₀⁻¹ versus [CAC]⁻¹ (Fig. 4) were plotted at various temperatures, obtaining straight lines passing through the origin. These graphs showed that the order relative to the substrate was first. The values of k₀ are shown in Table 2 at 303 K, 308 K, 313 K, 318K and 323 K.

Table 2: Effect of [Copper (II) asparagine]

10²[OH⁻] = 3.0 mol dm⁻³, 10⁴ [Fe(CN)₆]³⁻ = 20.0 mol dm⁻³ and μ = 1.0 mol dm⁻³

Temp. (K)	[Substrate] (mol dm ⁻³)					
	0.001	0.002	0.004	0.006	0.008	0.01
	10 ⁻² k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)					
303	0.865	1.884	2.995	4.865	6.169	10.926
308	1.324	2.176	3.359	7.876	9.994	14.754
313	2.288	3.886	5.346	13.688	17.475	22.934
318	3.544	5.796	7.674	16.886	21.768	25.687
323	4.235	6.957	9.656	20.385	25.785	30.574

Fig. 4: k₀⁻¹ vs [Substrate]⁻¹ graphs for the oxidation of CAC

Mechanism of oxidation of Copper (II) lysine complex (CAC)⁷:

Based on the kinetic data, the mechanism of uncatalyzed oxidation of CAC by alkaline hexacyanoferrate (III) is proposed as follows:

The rate of the reaction is represented in terms of disappearance of hexacyanoferrate (III)

Hence

$$-\frac{d[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = k_2 [\text{CAC}]^{2-} [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] \quad (5)$$

At high concentration of reactants, reaction was very fast. Assuming that,

$$[\text{CAC}]_T = [\text{CAC}] + [\text{CAC}]^{2-} \quad (6)$$

Hence,

$$[\text{CAC}] = [\text{CAC}]_T - [\text{CAC}]^{2-} \quad (7)$$

Applying steady state approximation for $[\text{CAC}]^{2-}$

$$\frac{d[\text{CAC}]^{2-}}{dt} = k_1[\text{CAC}][\text{OH}^-]^2 - k_{-1}[\text{CAC}]^{2-} - k_2[\text{CAC}]^{2-}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 0$$

$$\text{or } k_1([\text{CAC}]_T - [\text{CAC}]^{2-})[\text{OH}^-]^2 - k_{-1}[\text{CAC}]^{2-} - k_2[\text{CAC}]^{2-}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 0$$

$$k_1[\text{CAC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2 - k_1[\text{CAC}]^{2-}[\text{OH}^-]^2 - k_{-1}[\text{CAC}]^{2-} - k_2[\text{CAC}]^{2-}[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}] = 0$$

$$[\text{CAC}]^{2-}(k_1[\text{OH}^-]^2 + k_{-1} + k_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]) = k_1[\text{CAC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2$$

$$[\text{CAC}]^{2-} = \frac{k_1[\text{CAC}]_T[\text{OH}^-]^2}{k_1[\text{OH}^-]^2 + k_{-1} + k_2[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (8)$$

According to the stoichiometry of the reaction, 4 mol of $\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}$ were used per mol of CAC

Hence

$$k_o = - \frac{d [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{4k_1 k_2 [\text{CAC}]_T [\text{OH}^-]^2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{k_1 [\text{OH}^-]^2 + k_{-1} + k_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (10)$$

According to the experimental conditions and the observed results, it can be assumed that

$$k_1 [\text{OH}^-]^2 + k_{-1} \gg k_2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$$

$$k_o = - \frac{d [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{dt} = \frac{4k_1 k_2 [\text{CAC}]_T [\text{OH}^-]^2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]}{k_{-1} + k_1 [\text{OH}^-]^2} \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) confirms that the reaction is first-order with respect to $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]$ and CAC. Equation (11) can be represented as,

$$\frac{1}{k_o} = \frac{k_{-1} + k_1 [\text{OH}^-]^2}{4k_1 k_2 [\text{CAC}]_T [\text{OH}^-]^2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{k_o} = \frac{k_1}{4k_1 k_2 [\text{CAC}]_T [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} + \frac{k_{-1}}{4k_1 k_2 [\text{CAC}]_T [\text{OH}^-]^2 [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (13)$$

If we plot the graph between k_o^{-1} and $[\text{OH}^-]^2$, the intercept (I) and slope (S) of these plots can be represented by equations (14) and (15) respectively.

$$\text{Slope} = \frac{k_{-1}}{4k_1 k_2 [\text{CAC}]_T [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Intercept} = \frac{1}{4k_2 [\text{CAC}]_T [\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-}]} \quad (15)$$

Therefore,

$$\frac{\text{Intercept}}{\text{Slope}} = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} = K \quad (16)$$

Where $k_1/k_{-1} = K = \text{Equilibrium constant}$.

Conclusion

In the study of the oxidation of an amino acid metal complex (copper (II) asparagine) with hexacyanoferrate in alkaline medium, it was found that the reaction was first order with respect to the oxidant and substrate, and the order of the reaction with respect to $[\text{OH}^-]$ was less than one, which was confirmed by straight line plots of k_o versus $[\text{OH}^-]$. It was also observed that the rate of the reaction increased with increasing alkali and ionic strength.

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